

A Case Study on Tamaka Swasa W. S. R to Bronchial Asthma Ayurveda

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Abstract:- Tamaka Swasa is a type of Swasa Roga, affecting the Pranavaha Srotas, which is significantly distressing and a fatal disorder of the present-day life. Tamaka Swasa has been described in Ayurvedic Samhitas and seems to be identical to bronchial Asthma.¹ A Case of 64 year old male patient who presented with the symptoms of difficulty in breathing, tightness in chest, Cough with Whitish Color Sputum and generalized weakness. Tamaka Swasa was Treated by Internal Ayurvedic Medicine and Marked Improvement was seen. After 4 weeks of follow up no Episodes of above Complaints have been reported.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tamaka Swasa is a Pranavaha Sroto vikara. According to Acharya Charak it is considered as Yasya Vyadhi.² The sign & symptoms of Tamaka Swasa explained in Ayurvedic Samhitas. Tamas means darkness. Darkness in front of eyes is produced during the attack of this type of Swasa. Hence it is called as Tamaka Swasa.³ When Vata is obstructed by vitiated Kapha, it gets reversed and affects the Pranavaha Srotas.⁴ Both the Vata and Kapha have been considered to be the Doshas involved in the pathogenesis of Tamaka Swasa.⁵ The main features of Tamaka Swasa

Ghurghurak (wheezing or murmuring sound), Dyspnea, he is relieved (of restlessness) for sometimes soon after the phlegm comes out.⁶ There are two types of Tamaka Swasa, Pratamak and Santamak Swasa.⁷ Cough particularly at night or early morning. It is manageable in chronic stage and Curable if it is of recent onset.⁸

II. CASE REPORT

A 64 year old male patient came with the chief complaints of difficulty in breathing, chest discomfort and Cough specially at night or early morning and generalized weakness.

III. MATERIAL AND METHODS

• **Source of data** → Patient suffering from symptoms of Tamaka Swasa is selected from O.P.d of Dhanwantari Ayurvedic hospital Ujjain.

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• **Study design** - A single Case Study.

• **Clinical finding Subjective 2 Objective Parameter** →

Subjective Parameter-		
Symptoms	Before the treatment	30 the day of follow up
Cough	Continuous in day and night	Nil
Breathlessness	Present	Nil
Quantity of sputum	>10 ml	<2.5 ml
Objective Parameter		
R.R.	22/min.	20/min.
Breath Sounds	Wheezing Sound	No Wheeze

IV. TREATMENT

- Abyanga the back region with sukhousta mustard oil 10 ml + ½ gm Sandhava lavana and Nadi or pottali sweda.
- Khadiradi Vati twice a day.
- Kakkdashringi, Trikatu & mulethi churna twice in a day.
- Cap. Respiure twice in a day.
- Syp. Swasraj Twice in a day.

V. DISCUSSION

Asthma is one of the health conditions among children and adult. This condition is manifested by the aggravation of Pranavayu and obstruction of Kapha Dosha. So for the treatment of Swasa Roga substances which cause alleviation of Vata and Kapha Dosha has to be administered. Ushna virya drugs and substances possessing Vatanulomana properties are useful to treat this condition. In the beginning Tamaka Swasa patient has to be treated with unctuous fomentation therapies like Nadi-sveda, Prastara-Sveda and Sankara-Sweda etc, after anointing the body with oil mixed

with salt .This will helps to liquify the Kapha Dosha,which is adhered to the channel of circulation and there by it reduces the airway obstruction. when the channel of circulation purifies, Vata moves with ease through the channels.

In this patient Abhyanga is done with mustard oil mixed with Sandhav lavana followed by that Nadi- Sweda has been done. This has helped to remove the Kapha and relive airway obstruction. Khadiradi Vati 1BD daily and combinations of Kakdashringi churna ,Mulethi &Trikatu churna in the dose of 3gm daily before food as well as Respiure capsule twice daily ,has been given as the Shamanoushadhi.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on this case report, it can be said that Swasa Roga can be successfully managed by Ayurvedic treatment protocol. Combination of Snehana & Swedana for dissolving Kapha as well as removal of airway obstruction, and internal medicines possessing ushna virya and Vatanulomanaproperties can be administered for the efficient management of Swasa Roga.

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